

How the Work Environment Affects Employee Competence and its impact on Employee Performance? Survey of the Ministry of Religion of Sukabumi Regency, West Java Province, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: The aim is to examine the effect of the work environment on employee competencies and their impact on employee performance. Preliminary research shows the poor performance of employees of the Ministry of Religion in Sukabumi Regency, West Java Province. The survey was conducted on 208 respondents in the Department of Religion in Sukabumi District, West Java, Indonesia. Data were collected using a questionnaire and data analysis to test the t-test used. The analysis uses partial regression and hypothesis testing using a t-test. All analyzes use statistical tools using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS). The results show that the direction of effects of the Environment of Work (X) on Employee Competency (Y) is positive. Obtained p-value of 0,000 so that the p-value $\alpha = 0.05$. That the total effect of Employee Competency (Y) on Employee Performance (Z) is 0.764 or 76.4%. While the remaining 36.7% is the influence of other factors beyond Employee Competency. The results showed that the work environment plays an important role in realizing employee competencies and providing optimal employee performance.

Keywords: Work Environment, Employee Competence, Employee Performance, Significant Effect, SPSS, t-test, Important Role.

I. INTRODUCTION

The business environment is influenced by employee performance to achieve organizational goals. To make employee performance expected to be influenced by employee competence. Meanwhile, to achieve employee competence must be supported by an

adequate work environment. A preliminary survey of employees at the Ministry of Religion in Sukabumi Regency, West Java Province, showed a percentage of poor performance, so it can be said that the control environment, employee competence, and Employee Performance are not optimal in Table 1.

Tabel 1: Preliminary Survey.

No.	SB	B	KB	TB	STB	Total
Work Environment						
Frequency	178	148	118	34	2	480
Score	890	592	354	68	2	1906
Percentage	46.7	31	18.6	3.6	0.1	100
Employee Competency						
Frequency	136	73	171	63	37	480
Score	680	292	513	126	31	1642
Percentage	41,4	17.7	31.2	7.6	1.8	100
Employee Performance						
Frequency	36	52	41	16	5	150
Score	180	208	123	32	5	548
Percentage	32.8	37.9	22.4	5.8	0.9	100

Information: SB: Very Good, B: Good, KB: Less Good, TB: Not Good, STB: Very Unkind Data Processed from Questionnaire.

Previous studies relating to the work environment on competence [16-18]. This study tried to find its impact on performance.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Work Environment: Human resources in the organization will provide optimal results if supported by the work environment. Optimization of employee work will achieve its goals. There are two classifications of the work environment, namely the physical and non-physical environment [1]. Physical work is related to physical tasks [2-4]. Physical jobs related to the physical environment [5, 6]. While the non-physical work environment, good relations to the leadership and coworkers [7].

Employee Competence: The concept of competency, according to the American Psychological Industry Organization, is that the competency movement had begun in the 1960s and early 1970s [8]. Organizations must pay attention to the competencies of their employees to achieve their goals. Employee competence influences the quality of services and products produced [9, 10]. Skills can be interpreted as work concepts that are believed by a person or group as right or true. Manifest powers through typical work behaviour [11]. Competence will bring employees to work professionally [12].

Employee Performance: Performance is an action taken by employees. The production of employees includes the elements of Timeliness, Quantity, Quality, Attendance, and Ability to work in teams [13]. Employee

performance as an output, efficiency, and effectiveness are always associated with productivity [14]. Performance is a set of behaviours that are relevant to the goals of the organization where people work [15]. Three main factors affect the performance of employees, including the ability of an individual, level of effort expended, and organizational support [15, 22].

Work environment, employee competence, and employee performance: A right work environment will support employee competence [16-18]. Competence, which is an embodiment of employee professionalism, will create optimal performance [19-21]. The Work Environment can affect employee competence, and its impact on Employee Performance can be seen in Fig. 1.

Methods: This method uses analytic surveys and questionnaires as primary data collection tools. All administrative staff became the study population in the Ministry of Religion, Sukabumi District, West Java Province. The list of questions was distributed to 208 respondents. These questions cover 22 dimensions of 3 variables: work environment, employee competency, and employee performance. This study uses a "perfect" and "terrible" five-point scale to examine participants responding to questionnaire questions. Questionnaire testing to obtain validity and reliability. The analysis uses partial regression and hypothesis testing using a t-test. All analyzes use statistical tools using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validity and Reliability Test: Validity Recapitulation is shown in Table 2.

Fig. 1. Research Framework.

Table 2: Recapitulation Validity of Test Result.

Variables/Items	Corrected Item		
	Validity coefficient	R Tabel	Explanation
Work Environment			
X1	0.542	0.361	Valid
X2	0.753	0.361	Valid
X3	0.527	0.361	Valid
X4	0.520	0.361	Valid
X5	0.458	0.361	Valid
X6	0.851	0.361	Valid
X7	0.832	0.361	Valid
X8	0.608	0.361	Valid
X9	0.664	0.361	Valid
X10	0.730	0.361	Valid
X11	0.634	0.361	Valid
X12	0.704	0.361	Valid
X13	0.653	0.361	Valid

X14	0.883	0.361	Valid
X15	0.464	0.361	Valid
X16	0.616	0.361	Valid
Employee Competence			
Y1	0.251	0.361	Valid
Y2	0.706	0.361	Valid
Y3	0.502	0.361	Valid
Y4	0.553	0.361	Valid
Y5	0.441	0.361	Valid
Y6	0.847	0.361	Valid
Y7	0.829	0.361	Valid
Y8	0.600	0.361	Valid
Y9	0.714	0.361	Valid
Y10	0.772	0.361	Valid
Y11	0.643	0.361	Valid
Y12	0.618	0.361	Valid
Y13	0.372	0.361	Valid
Y14	0.798	0.361	Valid
Y15	0.919	0.361	Valid
Y16	0.900	0.361	Valid
Employee Performance			
Z1	0.448	0.361	Valid
Z2	0.624	0.361	Valid
Z3	0.414	0.361	Valid
Z4	0.414	0.361	Valid

Table 3: Recapitulation Reliability of Test Result.

Variable	Validity coefficient	R-Value Table	Explanation
	Value		
Work Environment	0.902	0.7	Reliable
Employee Competency	0.916	0.7	Reliable
Employee Performance	0.958	0.7	Reliable

Hypothesis Testing 1

The questionnaire about the Work Environment consisting of 16 statements with two dimensions, was declared valid because the validity coefficient value is higher than the r-table value of 0.361. The questionnaire about Employee Competency consisting of 16 statements with four dimensions was declared valid because the validity value was higher than the r-table value of 0.361. Survey on Employee Performance composed of 33 reports with six dimensions that were declared valid because the value of the validity coefficient was higher than the value of r-table that is 0.361.

The reliability test results of the research instruments can be seen in Table 3. Based on the reliability test results obtained, the reliability value for the reliability coefficient of the research instrument is more significant than 0.700, which means that all research variables are declared reliable or meet the requirements. Because the validity and reliability tests state that all variables are valid and reliable, it means that the instrument (questionnaire) used is accurate and reliable.

H1: The work environment significantly affects the competence of the employee. Based on Table 4, the effect of the Work Environment (X) on Employee Competency (Y) is positive. Obtained p-value of 0,000 so that the p-value $< \alpha = 0.05$. Its means that there is a positive and significant effect of the environment of work on Employee Competence

Hypothesis testing 2

H2: There is a significant effect on employee competence on employee performance. Table 4 shows that the total impact of Employee Competency (Y) on Employee Performance (Z) is 0.764 or 76.4%, while the remaining 36.7% is the influence of other factors beyond Employee Competency.

The environment of work has the effects of significant on employee competence: From the results of the analysis, work environment factors have a strong influence on employee competence. The work environment shows a trend of technological improvement and social change. Employees need to understand the pattern of this change. If human resource competency increases because facilities support it, the performance will increase at all employee levels.

Table 4: Hypotesis Testing Result.

Variable	Beta	t-count	P-Value	Label
Work Environment → Employee Competence	0.409	8.533	0	Significant
Employee competency → Employee Performance	0.876	25.822	0	Significant

Competition due to globalization is so tight then. Public service organizations are required to be able to move faster and more innovative than competitors. Employees must be encouraged by the work environment to have superior skills or competencies. The environment must set competency standards. The conditions faced and the achievements that have been achieved by the work environment, are sources for formulating competency standards.

Employee competence has an effect of significant on the performance of employees.

From the above analysis, it can be said that competence is an underlying characteristic of a person and is related to the effectiveness of the performance of the individual in his work. Ability is an adequate skill to carry out a task or as having the required skills & skills. Competence is a human characteristic related to the effectiveness of performance as a style of acting, behaving, and thinking. The ability of employees will create superior performance.

IV. FUTURE SCOPE

This research explains the effect of work environment variables on employee competencies and their impact on employee performance. In future studies, it will be better if the X variable is developed, so that the research results will be more comprehensive.

V. CONCLUSION

This study aims to determine the effect of the environment of work on employee competence and its impact on employee performance in the Ministry of Religion, Sukabumi Regency, West Java Province. Hypothesis testing results indicate that the environment of work has an effect of significant on employee competence and impacts employee performance. This result can be interpreted that the work climate plays an important role in realizing employee competencies so that employee performance is getting more optimal.

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